

DEVELOPMENT OF IMPROVED METHODS FOR CHARACTERISING THE CURE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Ana Yong^{1,2}, Graham D. Sims¹, Stephen L. Ogin² Paul Smith² and Sam J. P. Gnaniah¹

¹National Physical Laboratory, Hampton Road, Teddington, Middlesex,
TW11 0LW, United Kingdom
Email: ana.yong@npl.co.uk
Email : graham.sims@npl.co.uk

²Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences, University of Surrey
Guildford, GU2 7XH, United Kingdom
Email: p.smith@surrey.ac.uk
Email : s.ogin@surrey.ac.uk

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy materials cured to four different states have been studied using Dynamic Mechanical Analysis, Differential Scanning Calorimetry and Thermomechanical Analysis. It is well known that measured values of the glass transition temperature (T_g) using these techniques show poor agreement. The T_g was measured using a new multiple heating rate method that aims to eliminate the effects of thermal lag, often cited as a cause of disagreement between these thermal analysis techniques. This new method enables the extrapolation of the value for the T_g at zero heating rate, which has been used in this work to draw comparison between DSC, TMA and DMA independently of heating rate and thermal lag effects. The effects of the degree of cure on the measurement and value of the T_g have been studied and are presented alongside the effects of heating rate dependence.

1 INTRODUCTION

Further improvements in the cost-effectiveness and reliability in composite materials manufacturing is a key requirement for the current and potential user sectors for these materials. An important element of this is developing better methods for measurement of the parameters that characterize the degree of cure of a composite part. Improvements in these methods will, as a result, enable more effective implementation of cure monitoring technologies. One of the major obstacles to cure monitoring technology is the poor precision and agreement between data obtained at different sites. The lack of precision can arise due to a number of factors, including differences in instrument calibration, experimental procedure and the approaches used to analyse data.

This study investigates thermal analysis techniques as a widely used technique for cure assessment. One approach is Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), which is used to determine a number of parameters, including the glass transition temperature (T_g). The T_g is represented as a single value, but in reality the glass transition occurs over a broad temperature range. As a result, published data show that values of T_g reported by different researchers may vary significantly for the same material depending on measurement method and interpretation of data. In a recent standard, ISO 6721-11 [1], a new method for the measurement of T_g by DMA was published that is based on using multiple heating rates. In this method, the material is tested at three different heating rates and the measured T_g values are plotted as a function of heating rate. The results are then extrapolated in order to obtain the T_g for zero heating rate (0 °C/min), which eliminates the effects of thermal lag. Thermal lag can occur due to

the temperature of the specimen not having reached the temperature of the oven, which is the reported temperature as measured by a thermocouple (i.e. not the surface or internal temperature of the specimen).

As a further investigation into the effect of heating rate on data precision, this paper compares DMA with two other techniques; Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA), using the multiple heating rate method. The T_g was measured using each of these techniques for the purpose of developing an understanding of thermal analysis measurements and their suitability for off-line use in cure monitoring. While methodology is a contributing factor to the lack of precision, differences in the way the instruments themselves measure changes at the glass transition can also lead to variation in results. This work presents an initial insight into the link between the techniques and how they relate to the state of cure of a composite.

Achieving optimum cure during the manufacture of a composite material is necessary in order to realise the full mechanical performance of a composite material.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The material used was a unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy composite, which was cured as 2 mm thick, 16 ply panels at four different temperatures. Using the recommended 3°C/min heating rate, the panels were held for 2 hours at 150°C, 160°C, 170°C and 180°C (c.f. recommended cure temperature is 175°C) in order to produce specimens at different states of cure.

2.2 Specimen preparation

DMA specimens, 35 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm, were tested in the longitudinal direction, with fibres parallel to the length of the specimen. Dimensional changes were measured in the through-thickness direction of 10 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm TMA specimens. DSC specimens were cut to fit TA Instruments Tzero Aluminium crucibles (5 mm diameter) and then smoothed on one surface to ensure optimal contact with the base of the crucible and sensor platform containing a thermocouple. The approximate mass of each specimen was 10 mg. Finally, 10 mm × 30 mm × 2 mm specimens were prepared in line with the new DBS test method. These specimens were prepared with the fibres parallel to the length of the specimen.

The test specimens were dried for seven days at 80°C to minimize any effect of moisture on the T_g of the specimens. After drying, the specimens were kept in a controlled environment at 23°C ± 2°C and 50% ± 5% RH prior to testing.

2.3 Measurements by DMA

DMA data given in this paper were obtained using the TA Instruments Q800 instrument. Tests were carried out in static air using the single cantilever beam configuration at constant displacement, with oscillation amplitude 10 µm and frequency 1 Hz. In this instance, separate specimens were heated from 30°C to 250°C at rates of 3, 5 and 10°C/min.

The glass transition temperature can be obtained from DMA data using any of a number of data analysis points. The most widely used include the onset point or inflection point of the storage modulus curve, the peak of the tan delta curve and the peak of the loss modulus curve, shown in Figure 1. These values are derived from the analyzed complex modulus following the relationships outlined in the figure, where the complex modulus is calculated from the measured load and displacement data following:

$$E^* = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where δ is the phase angle seen in Figure 1, ε is the measured strain, and σ is the stress. For the purposes of this work, following recommendations in ISO 6721-11, the T_g was taken to be the inflection point of the storage modulus curve. The results were then plotted on a graph of T_g against heating rate and then extrapolated in order to find the T_g for zero heating rate, known as the $T_{g(0)}$.

Figure 1: Typical DMA analysis points for the measurement of T_g

2.4 Measurements by TMA

TMA was performed using the TA Instruments Q400 instrument in expansion mode with a preload force of 0.05 N. Dimensional changes were measured in the through-thickness direction from 30°C to 250°C, at heating rates of 3, 5 or 10°C/min. The value for the T_g was taken as the midpoint of the transition region, as in the example given in Figure 2, following the analysis method outlined in ISO 11359-2:1999 [2]. The T_g values were then plotted against the heating rates and the value for the T_g at zero heating rate was found by extrapolation.

Figure 2: Analysis point for measurement of T_g by TMA

2.5 Measurements by DSC

DSC measurements were performed using the TA Instruments Q2000 instrument under a nitrogen gas flow of 50 ml/min. The instrument was calibrated using indium temperature reference standard (NIST 2232). Specimens were heated from 30°C to 250°C at a heating rate of either 5°C/min, 10°C/min or 20°C/min. Higher heating rates than those used in the DMA and TMA measurements were used in the DSC following recommendations in ISO 11357-2:2014 [3]. The DSC measures changes in heat flow as a function of temperature, where an example of the resulting data is shown in Figure 3. The T_g is taken as the inflection point of this curve. The subsequent exothermic peak results from the additional cure reaction taking place, which can be used as a measure of the degree of cure [4]. The degree of cure is calculated using the equation;

$$\text{Degree of cure (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{H_S}{H_T}\right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where H_S is the total heat of reaction of the partially cured sample and H_T is the total heat of reaction of an uncured prepreg sample. In order to obtain the total heat of reaction, DSC was performed on the uncured prepreg material at a heating rate of 5°C/min.

Figure 3: Typical DSC curve for under-cured CFRP

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DMA, TMA and DSC measurements using the multiple heating rate test method

Figure 5 shows the graph of storage modulus inflection point against heating rate for DMA, where the “apparent” T_g was taken as the inflection point of the storage modulus curve and $T_{g(0)}$ is derived from the intercept. The values for the T_g at zero heating rate are given in Table 1. It is seen that as cure progresses in the polymer resin matrix, the glass transition temperature increases. This is due to increased crosslinking in the epoxy matrix, which causes a rise in the glass transition temperature. The dependence of the measured value of the T_g on the heating rate used can also be seen, with approximately a ten degree difference between the T_g measured at a heating rate of 3°C/min and that measured at 10°C/min. This highlights the need for the new method proposed in ISO 6721-11, where interlaboratory trials in previous work have shown that the 0°C extrapolated value is the most reproducible between different users at different sites [1]. This new method enables improved reproducibility of data.

Figure 5: Graph of effect of heating rate on T_g as measured by DMA

Cure Temperature (°C)	$T_{g(0)}$ (°C)	Temperature-Heating Rate Plot Gradient (min)
150	148	2.76
160	164	2.96
170	181	2.49
180	191	2.25

Table 1: $T_{g(0)}$ values measured by DMA

TMA data for this material required a more in-depth analysis than outlined in standard ISO 11359-2:1999 [2] for the determination of T_g by TMA. In the graph of dimension change against temperature shown in Figure 6, it can be seen that the gradient of the curve changes at two points, an effect which was seen in all of the specimens. The dimension change of a polymer matrix composite at the T_g is associated with a change in free volume at a chain end, therefore this effect may be attributed to initial movement of chains that are not fully cross-linked as a result of the material not being fully cured [5]. From the plot of the derivative of the curve, the two transitions become more clearly seen. In this instance, the T_g was taken as the onset point of the second gradient change.

Figure 6: TMA data for CFRP

The graph seen in Figure 7 shows the data for the T_g obtained by TMA plotted against the heating rate used. From comparing the slope of the temperature-heating rate plots it is clear that the TMA data exhibits low heating rate dependence. As with DMA, the difference between the T_g values at the different stages of cure can be seen, with the values for $T_{g(0)}$ given in Table 2. The gradient of the plot for the material cured at 170°C is a negative value; however this could be attributed to a single outlier in the TMA data for measurements at 10°C/min which was lower than the rest.

Figure 7: Graph of effect of heating rate on T_g measured by TMA

Cure Temperature (°C)	$T_{g(0)}$ (°C)	Temperature-Heating Rate Plot Gradient (min)
150	139	1.35
160	156	0.72
170	178	-0.02
180	187	0.54

Table 2: $T_{g(0)}$ values for TMA

DSC was used to measure the degree of cure and glass transition temperature of each material. DSC measurements of the uncured prepreg material confirmed that the matrix resin was a polymer blend, seen as two overlapping exothermic peaks. In the DSC data obtained from the partially cured panels, the first peak was no longer visible, demonstrating progression of the crosslinking that occurs during the cure reaction. The degree of cure of each panel is given in Table 3, where it can be seen that full cure has not been achieved, as given by this method, in the panel which was cured above the manufacturer specified temperature of 175°C.

Cure Temperature (°C)	Degree of Cure (%)
150	76
160	83
170	90
180	98

Table 3: Degree of cure of CFRP specimens

The glass transition temperature as measured by DSC has been plotted against heating rate in Figure 8. The value for $T_{g(0)}$ and gradient of the plot are presented in Table 4. It is seen in the figure that the heating rate dependence of the T_g varies for each sample, however it is still low. Small specimen sizes in DSC reduce the effect of thermal lag when compared with DMA.

Analysis of the T_g of filled materials such as CFRP using DSC is far less straightforward than TMA and DMA due to the low volume fraction of resin (the active part of the material composition), which results in poor sensitivity to the glass transition. DSC measurements of such reinforced materials are, in addition, greatly affected by specimen preparation, where good contact must be made between the specimen and the crucible, which sit above the thermocouple.

Figure 8: Graph of effect of heating rate on T_g measured by DSC

Cure Temperature (°C)	$T_{g(0)}$ (°C)	Temperature-Heating Rate Plot Gradient (min)
150	128	0.03
160	131	0.45
170	145	1.27
180	173	0.25

Table 4: $T_{g(0)}$ values for DSC

3.2 Comparison of results from the thermal analysis techniques

The graph in Figure 9 shows the comparison between the values obtained for the T_g at zero heating rate plotted against degree of cure for each of the three thermal analysis techniques. The values from this graph are presented in Table 5. From this data we can see that the lowest values are obtained by DSC, followed by TMA and lastly DMA. The difference between the values can result from a number of factors, including difference in sample size. The new multiple heating rate method accounts for thermal lag and as a result discounts differences due to sample size, however there remains a large discrepancy in the extrapolated values for T_g . The measured T_g value from different thermal analysis techniques, in addition to differences in experimental setup, varies due to the fact that they each measure a different material property, showing different responses, or sensitivity, to the glass transition.

The increase in glass transition temperature between 90% and 98% cure of the specimens shown in the graph indicates the effect that reaching full cure can have and highlights the need to characterize this process during composite manufacture.

Measurements obtained by DMA show a much clearer and higher dependence on the heating rate used, due to the thermal lag effect [6], than measurements by DSC and TMA, as seen in Table 5. DSC specimens are smaller in size and remain in closer contact with the thermocouple than the specimens used in the other two techniques, and are therefore less affected by thermal lag.

DSC measurements of the uncured prepreg material showed evidence of a polymer blend as the matrix resin, which was seen as two exothermic peaks. Similarly, two transition regions were observed in the TMA measurements, which can be attributed to two separate, measurable changes in free volume, which results from the movement at polymer chain ends.

Figure 9: Graph of the effect of degree of cure on $T_{g(0)}$ measurement by DSC, TMA and DMA

Cure Temperature (°C)	Degree of Cure (%)	DMA		TMA		DSC	
		T _{g(0)} (°C)	Gradient (min)	T _{g(0)} (°C)	Gradient (min)	T _{g(0)} (°C)	Gradient (min)
150	76	148	2.76	139	1.35	128	0.03
160	83	164	2.96	156	0.72	131	0.45
170	90	181	2.49	178	-0.02	145	1.27
180	98	191	2.25	187	0.54	173	0.25

Table 5: Comparison of T_{g(0)} values for DMA, TMA and DSC

4 CONCLUSIONS

A new, multiple heating rate method was used for measurement of the glass transition temperature by DMA, TMA and DSC. It was observed that T_g measurements by DMA were much more dependent on heating rate than TMA and DSC. Comparison of the results showed poor agreement for the value of the T_g between techniques, which is probably related to the fact that each technique measures a different parameter from which the glass transition temperature can be identified. T_g values measured by DSC were much lower than those measured by TMA and DMA, which could suggest that from the onset of chain movement related to the glass transition, a large change in heat flux occurs well before the critical point for the changes measured in stiffness and free volume that result from increased chain mobility. This indicates that the DSC is more sensitive to the onset of chain mobility at the glass transition. Further work is planned to confirm these observations. Using the multiple heating rate method for DMA minimizes the variation between data obtained at different sites and by different researchers. In addition the curves shown in Figure 5 can be used as a calibration tool for obtaining data at other heating rates. Due to the complexity of resin systems, further work will be required in order to understand the relationship between the resin chemistry and measurement techniques.

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